

Safety Risk Analysis in Mega Projects – A Case Study

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Abstract: The construction industry's technology is evolving at a rapid pace around the globe. Nowadays, the construction sector in India is mostly focused on mega projects. Mega projects are distinct, exceptional, and unique in the building business. These megaprojects are expensive, perhaps exceeding \$1 billion USD, have a complex structure, and present additional obstacles. According to some analysts, the minimal cost of a megaproject equals 0.01% of the country's GDP. Mega projects are rapidly expanding in India, with distinct building technologies, techniques, processes, and architectural elements. These megaprojects contribute to the country's development, improve living conditions, and so on. Because of the increased complexity and length of time required to complete construction activities, this type of project introduces a variety of hazards at various phases of development. This may result in a change in the scope of the project, a delay in the project, or even termination of the project. Losses may also arise. Among these dangers, the most critical type is on-site safety risk, which should be treated as a major issue. If this on-site safety risk is ignored, both the project contractor and the client will suffer significant losses. Neglecting safety factors may result in fatalities, faulty construction, project delays, and an increase in project costs. It may potentially result in the discontinuation of the project. So, on-site safety should be prioritized and considered the most crucial component in building. Due to these circumstances, a safety risk assessment should be conducted. The current research study examines the various forms of dangers that may arise during project building on-site. It splits the sorts of risks into two categories based on the type of construction. This analysis is conducted utilizing three distinct methodologies. Each risk is assessed and quantified independently, and ranks are assigned based on severity, probability, and effect level.

Keywords: Megaproject, risk assessment, technologies, project complexity, probability, Impact level

Introduction

General

Risks in building projects are widespread, particularly on construction sites, from the planning stage to the closure stage, and occasionally even after the close. Boundless hazards arise primarily during the construction phase, but there are also a huge number of opportunistic behaviors in construction projects that result in numerous risk events. According to a recent report in India, 38 accidents occur every day on building sites. Risk management methods emerge only through practice in dealing with unpredictability and uncertainty. Risk management in construction projects is seen as a critical step for achieving project objectives such as time, cost, quality, safety, and environmental sustainability, among others. If we identify the risks before the project begins, we can easily manage/mitigate the risk and reduce

the outflow of losses to the greatest extent possible. The current research paper discussed risk-related aspects of safety and building project procedures. The term "safety risk" refers to the projected likelihood and severity of a hazard's repercussions or outcomes in any construction-related incident.

Risk assessments are an essential component of every occupational health and safety management plan. Assessing risk in the early stages of a project helps to avert future difficulties and reduces additional complexities. This will make things run more smoothly over time. The purpose of this research is to determine the benefits of completing risk assessments in project management, which include reducing project risk exposure and making accurate and unambiguous decisions on crucial topics throughout each phase of the project. The purpose of using multiple risk assessment methodologies is to analyse various types of risks in various activities and assign ranks to each activity, making it easier to determine the risk's impact on the project. The top-ranked risks will be recognised, and a solution will be developed quickly in order for the project to run smoothly. So that the project is not stalled owing to noncompliance with safety regulations. The fulfilment of safety compliances is critical in any building project.

Risk has been properly assessed and incorporated into project designs, resulting in risk reduction in megaprojects. The goal is to gather information about potential dangers that may arise during the project's on-site erection, analysing each risk using three separate methodologies. These methods determine the priorities of the risks associated with each activity, and the ranks obtained using these methods are correlated using the Rank Correlation Coefficient (RCC) method to determine the accuracy of the ranks, resulting in a better decision-making process and a higher project success rate.

Objective of Research

To identify and analyze the potential risk factors to cause harm (hazard identification). Analyze and evaluate the risk associated with that hazard (risk analysis, and risk evaluation). Categorizing activities into technical and non-technical risks, determining the effect of risks on the project by allocating ranking to each activity.

Literature Review

Transnational public-private partnerships (TPPPs) have emerged as a significant means for construction and investment firms to invest in other nations. This article focusses mostly on identifying and evaluating risk factors in TPPP initiatives. This research contributes to a better understanding of the risk elements in TPPP projects and might be valuable to risk management professionals and researchers. This paper discusses risk assessment in private-public partnerships (PPPs). The tool FAHP method, which is an extended form of the analytic hierarchy process and fuzzy analytic hierarchy process techniques, is explained, as is the establishment for evaluating the TPPP project risk level and the risk assessment procedure. The key dangers identified in the study are outlined Yu et.,al(2018).

In China, megaproject risk is addressed through risk allocation between the public and private sectors. This research also aids in risk response planning and control for future projects in China. In China, the risk rankings for the PPP mode are compared between the public, private, and academic sectors Chan AP et.,al (2011).

A questionnaire survey is done, and research data is gathered from Chinese building industry professionals, designers, contractors, and designers. IBM SPSS software is used to analyse the five key characteristics of megaproject success. The fuzzy set theory is used to evaluate the usefulness of key performance indicators. Second, a questionnaire survey is conducted, and third, fuzzy theory is used to develop important performance indicators for evaluating the effectiveness of mega projects. This study assists megaproject construction practitioners in better understanding the factors that contribute to megaproject success He Q et al (2021). Preventing claims and disputes over different site conditions (DSCs) is key in minimising geotechnical hazards Dawoody et.,al (2022). The available study focusses mostly on crises in megaprojects and the tactics employed to address them. The case under discussion is the Islamabad-Rawalpindi Metro, a Pakistani mega project Iftikhar R et.,al (2022).

Rail infrastructure projects are extremely complicated and capital-intensive, involving numerous stakeholders. As a result, effective risk management is critical to the success of these types of projects. Most train projects in developing countries, such as India, will be delayed and overbudget. This study was undertaken by the Indian construction sector, and 31 risk attributes were discovered. The survey was done, and the replies were thoroughly evaluated using descriptive statistics such as the relative importance index, analysis of variance, and factor analysis Singh S et., al (2022). The identification of construction risks indicates which dangers are relevant to the current investigation and which are not. The customer selected an engineering and project management consultant (EPMC) to handle the development and construction of a shipping port and container terminal Joubert and Pretoris (2020). Understanding the workflow and decision-making process, which provides a road map for developing new software solutions to assist them in better identifying and communicating risks throughout project execution, hence improving project performance Xie H et., al(2022).Met network modelling shed light on the intricate interaction between international construction hazards and long-term project success. Then, using the risk relationship network and risk event network, the root cause of risk occurrence should be identified and the risk's continuity controlled Liu et.,al (2021).This study serves as the foundation for a systematic approach to risk classification and the creation of a shared risk registry based on data from prior initiatives. While the analytical performed in this study is specific to scientific research facility projects, the methodologies and approach can be used with any sort of project risk data Dicks and Molenaar (2022).

Knowledge exchange among numerous participants in megaproject management. While sharing knowledge, similar mistakes can be avoided, work efficiency can be improved, and the danger of failure can be reduced, all of which will improve megaproject performance due to the complex relationships and information flows among the various participants that offer a

problem in megaproject management. According to the findings of this study's empirical research, subjective norms and perceived behavior control are positively connected with the behavioral purpose of knowledge sharing, whereas the impacts of attitude have not been confirmed Li et., al (2022). To collect data, a questionnaire survey is administered to working professionals involved in large-scale initiatives. A secondary confirmatory model is created by structural equation modelling. This paper assists project managers, safety management, and stakeholders in identifying hazard areas that require improvement and mitigating risks Jia et.,al (2022).

This paper also includes a case study that discusses how to use the suggested conceptual system model and SNA approach to prioritize the complexity of O&M or MTPs, as well as how to validate the model and method Zhu et.,(202).

Most mega projects subject their stakeholders, particularly insurance firms and company owners, to on-site construction risks for a variety of reasons. This research provides insight into onsite risk management in the context of stakeholders and owners, as well as a way for practically implementing active risk management in mega projects to achieve risk control liang et., al (2011). This study addresses the implementation of a public meg project public building safety assessment system in China, which includes inspections, inspection methods, inspection processes, inspection organization, inspectors, and legal research xue et., al (202). Mirror Z is the method employed for decision makers. The results of the problems revealed public concerns about a wide range of issues, including government cooperation, environmental impacts, commercial development, alignment options, financing arrangements, operational arrangements, construction and design, and even the sustainable development of local towns and infrastructure Sherman et., al (2021). The investigation found no link between NRC region and risk. Risks are a common feature that exists in all types of locations, with no association between region and risk existence. During the research, it is also proven that design risk is the most common risk among the four reactor manufacturers represented in the dataset Erol et., al (2020)

This study looked into the relationship between complexity and risk in megaprojects. The quantitative analysis revealed elements that were more closely related to the change in scores for particular risk factors. As a result, an integrated risk assessment approach (IRAP) was proposed to assist megaproject practitioners in developing more effective risk management strategies. The findings of this study were based on large-scale building projects, but they could also apply to other sorts of projects Wang et., al (2021), Xu et., al (2020).

Megaprojects today are too complex, tremendously expensive, and involve more risk. So, safety management varies from project to project and interacts with one another. This research proposes a hybrid technique for dynamic stimulation of risk variables. This study examines accident investigations to determine risk factors and their interactions. To determine the overtime risk variables, the probability exposure and consequence (LEC) technique is applied. A system dynamic model is also utilized. In this study, the safety risk stimulation method is

clearly presented, and a flow chart depicts a three-stage risk identification procedure. To rank the risk factors, a sensitivity analysis method is applied. Following that, the model is applied to the urban rail transit construction system project in Shenzhen, China. The experiments are performed and discussed Darwis et., al (2021). To assess occupational safety and health in one of Hesamuddin University's projects, the analysis determined that construction activities had 23 dangers that have been analyzed to identify the level of risk and risk value. According to the findings, the five most risky significant building activities are as follows Mahalingam and Levitt (2007).

The thorough case studies of four comparable global infrastructure projects show that legislative rules, cultural values, and the current economic position in the founding nations all influence project participants' perceptions of safety P Muralidhar (2018). Clashes in projects caused by conflicting mindsets result in delays and expenditures. This research contributes to practice by identifying challenges that international contractors face when attempting to transfer safety techniques for developing countries on short-term global projects, as well as theory by shedding light on the various cultural challenges encountered on global projects.

Literature gap

Due to the evaluation of all articles, a grasp of risk management in the construction industry in numerous ways such as risk in safety, management, design, and so on, done using various methodologies, aids in the analysis of risks in megaprojects. In India, dangers in building operations are prevalent, particularly on construction sites. Risk events cannot be predicted. Only by practicing how to deal with uncertainty will risk management approaches evolve. If we recognize the risk before the start of the project, we can easily control it and avoid losses to the greatest extent possible. The current thesis examines the safety risks in megaprojects using three methods: 1. Weighted sum method (WSM), Relative important index (RII), Technique for Order Performance by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS), and determining the accuracy of the ranks by comparing them using the Rank Correlation Coefficient (RCC) method, which saves money and time.

Methodology

WSM/SAW Method:

The Simple Additive Weighing method, often referred as weighted linear combination or scoring approaches, is a popular multi-attribute decision-making tool. This method is simple to implement because it does not use any sophisticated algorithms. This method is well-known and widely used in multi-attribute decision making (MADM). This SAW method is part of the MADM process, in which decision makers must apply weights to each attribute.

$$A = \sum_{j=1}^m W_j(X_{ij})$$

Where as W_j = Weight and X_{ij} = Summation of N - Matrix

RII method:

The RII approach is used to assess the significance of the many causes and consequences of delays. The relative importance index analysis was used in this study to evaluate the criteria based on their relative significance. The relative index can be calculated using the following formula:

$$\sum \frac{W}{A * N}$$

W = Risk impact level, A = Highest weight and N = total no. of observations

Likert scale ranged from 1 (unlikely) to 5 (certain) is used in this study. This method is used to calculate the relative relevance indexes for different risks.

3.3 TOPSIS method:

This considers both the distance to the positive ideal solution and the distance to the negative ideal solution when calculating their relative proximity. Alternate priority orders can be achieved by comparing the relative distance. This strategy is regularly used to wrap up the decision-making process. This is due to the truth that the concept is uncomplicated, easy to comprehend, computes quickly, and facilitates the comparison of the relative effectiveness of different solutions.

Step 1: Calculate Normalised Matrix $\bar{X}_{ij} = \frac{X_{ij}}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n X_{ij}^2}}$

Step 2: Calculate weighted Normalised Matrix

$V_{ij} = \bar{X}_{ij} \times W_j$

Step 3: Calculate the ideal best and ideal worst value

$$S_i^+ = \left[\sum_{j=1}^m (V_{ij} - V_j^+)^2 \right]^{0.5}$$

Step 4: Calculate the Euclidean distance from the ideal best

Step 5: Calculate Performance Score $P_i = \frac{S_i^-}{S_i^+ + S_i^-}$

Results and Discussions

WSM and SAW method:

Using WSM and SAW method, ranks for all the activities are calculated based on their probability of occurrence value and its severity on the project. The ranks for these activities are known based on the Ai values and based on these values the ranks are allocated to the activities and are arranged in ascending order in Table 4.

Table 4: Ranks based on Risk impact level

WSM/SAW						
Activities	Probability	Severity	Risk impact/level	Ai	rank	accurate rank
Welding spatters	5	5	25	0.99	1	1
Lifting coils/Loading coil depend	4	5	20	0.858	2	2
Use of Threading machine	4	5	20	0.858	2	3
Strand cutting	4	5	20	0.858	2	4
Stressing	4	5	20	0.858	2	5
Flying particles, noise, dust, moving parts, untrained operators.	4	5	20	0.858	2	6
No approved plan and design	4	5	20	0.858	2	7
Receiving, offloading storage of posttensioning Equipment and materials	4	4	16	0.7392	8	8
Manual handling	4	4	16	0.7392	8	9
Grouting	4	4	16	0.7392	8	10
Emergency Resuse Response	4	4	16	0.7392	8	11
Electricity	3	5	15	0.726	12	12
Fire and/or explosion when cylinder are stationed for use	3	5	15	0.726	12	13
welding and gas cutting works	3	4	12	0.6204	14	14
-09764XV NM.,[P0875412`1`Lifting/Offloading of material by lifting equipment`]\086R		3	12	0.6204	14	16
Formwork Installation including shuttering & de- shuttering	4	3	12	0.6204	14	17
Night Shift Work	4	3	12	0.6204	14	18
Shifting and placing by crane/gantry	3	4	12	0.6204	14	19
Placing of shuttering on bed	3	4	12	0.6204	14	20

In these technological risks, Ai values are determined for each action. The Ai values fluctuate according to the probability and severity of the activity. Every step is assigned a rank based on its Ai value. Here Some activities have the same Ai value and hence share the same rank. As a result, we estimated the accurate rank using Excel to ensure that the activities received proper rankings. Based on these rankings, the influence on the project is determined, and appropriate measures are put in place to reduce or mitigate the risk.

The table 4 shows that the 2nd rank has 6 activities, the 8th rank has 4, the 12th level has 2, and the 14th rank has 17 activities, all of which share the same rank. It is so because the likelihood and severity of the activities are equal. As a result, the Ai value is the same for all of these actions. As a result, they share the same rank for several activities.

Non-Technical Risks:

Using the WSM and SAW approaches ranks for all activities are generated based on their likelihood of occurrence and impact on the project. The Ai values establish the ranks for these activities, which are then assigned to the activities and planned in ascending order in Table 5.

Table 5 Non-Technical Risks using WSM/SAW

WSM/SAW						
Activities	Probability	Severity	Risk impact/level	Ai	rank	accurate rank
Slip, trip, and falls	5	5	25	0.99	1	1
eye irritation from radiation	5	5	25	0.99	1	2
Adverse weather condition	4	5	20	0.858	3	3
Extreme high winds, heat, humidity	4	5	20	0.858	3	4
head, eye, hearing, foot, hand injuries	4	5	20	0.858	3	5
work platform	4	5	20	0.858	3	6
radiated heat	4	5	20	0.858	3	7
gas leaks	4	5	20	0.858	3	8
flash back	4	5	20	0.858	3	9
Chemical handling storage disposal	4	4	16	0.7392	10	10
Summer works	4	4	16	0.7392	10	11
unprotected voids	4	4	16	0.7392	10	12
extreme weather	3	5	15	0.726	13	13
fragile surface	3	5	15	0.726	13	14
General site activities	4	3	12	0.6204	15	15

In these non-technical risks, the Ai values are estimated for everyone's activity. The Ai values differ according to how likely and severity of the activity. Each action is assigned a rank based on its Ai value. Here Some activities have a save Ai value, thus they share the same rank. As a result, we estimated the accurate rank using Excel to ensure that the activities received proper rankings. Based on these rankings, the influence on the project is determined, and sufficient measures are implemented to reduce or mitigate the risk. As seen in the table above, the first rank has two activities, the third rank has seven, the tenth rank has three, and the thirteenth rank has two, all of which share the same ranks. It is due to the likelihood and the gravity of

the events are equal. As a result, the A_i value is the same for all of these actions. As a result, they share the same rank for several activities.

The RII Method

In this RII method, we compare the effects of actions based on their likelihood and severity scores. RII values for each activity are calculated using a formula and determined. Table 6 shows the ranks provided for each activity based on respective RII values.

Table 6. Technical risks using RII

RII METHOD						
Activities	Probability	Severity	Risk impact/ level	RII value	rank	accurate rank
Welding spatters	5	5	25	0.0178571	1	1
Lifting coils/Loading coil dependder	4	5	20	0.0142857	2	2
Use of Threading machine	4	5	20	0.0142857	2	3
Strand cutting	4	5	20	0.0142857	2	4
Stressing	4	5	20	0.0142857	2	5
Flying particles, noise, dust, moving parts, untrained operators.	4	5	20	0.0142857	2	6
No approved plan and design	4	5	20	0.0142857	2	7
Receiving, offloading storage of posttensioning Equipment and materials	4	4	16	0.0114285	8	8
Manual handling	4	4	16	0.0114285	8	9
Grouting	4	4	16	0.0114285	8	10
Emergency Resuse Response	4	4	16	0.0114285	8	11
Electricity	3	5	15	0.0107142	12	12
Fire and/or explosion when cylinder are stationed for use	3	5	15	0.0107142	12	13
welding and gas cutting works	3	4	12	0.0107142	14	14

Mobilization/demobilization of plant and equipment to/from site	4	3	12	0.0107142	14	15
Lifting/Offloading of material by lifting equipment	4	3	12	0.0107142	14	16
Formwork Installation including shuttering & de-shuttering	4	3	12	0.0107142	14	17
Night Shift Work	4	3	12	0.0107142	14	18
Shifting and placing by crane/gantry	3	4	12	0.0107142	14	19
Placing of shuttering on bed	3	4	12	0.0107142	14	20

In these technological hazards, RII values are calculated for every action taken. The RII levels fluctuate according to the possibility and degree of severity of the activity. The RII values determine the Ranks assigned to each activity. Here Some activities have a save RII value, thus they share the same rank. As a result, we estimated the accurate rank using Excel to ensure that the activities received proper rankings. Based on these rankings, the effect on the project is determined, and appropriate measures are implemented to reduce or minimise the risk. The table 6 shows that the second rank has 6 activities, the eighth rank has 4 activities, the twelfth rank has 2 activities, and the fourteenth rank has 7 activities, all with the same rank. It is because the likelihood and severity of the activities are equal. Hence, the RII value is the same for those actions. As a result, they share the same rank for several activities.

Non-technical Risk: This RII method evaluates the impact of activities based on their probability and severity. RII values for each activity are calculated using a formula and determined. Table 7 assigns ranks based on RII values for each activity.

Table. 7 Non-Technical risk using RII

RII METHOD						
Activities	Probability	Severity	Risk impact/level	RII value	rank	accurate rank
slip, trip, and falls	5	5	25	0.05263157	1	1
eye irritation from radiation	5	5	25	0.05263157	1	2
Adverse weather condition	4	5	20	0.04210526	3	3
Extreme high winds, heat, humidity	4	5	20	0.04210526	3	4

head, eye, hearing, foot, hand injuries	4	5	20	0.04210526	3	5
work platform	4	5	20	0.04210526	3	6
radiated heat	4	5	20	0.04210526	3	7
gas leaks	4	5	20	0.04210526	3	8
flash back	4	5	20	0.04210526	3	9
Chemical handling storage disposal	4	4	16	0.033684	10	10
Summer works	4	4	16	0.033684	10	11
unprotected voids	4	4	16	0.033684	10	12
extreme weather	3	5	15	0.031579	13	13
fragile surface	3	5	15	0.031579	13	14
General site activities	4	3	12	0.025263	15	15

In those technological hazards, RII values are calculated for each action. The RII levels fluctuate according to the probability and degree of severity of the activity. The RII values determine the Ranks assigned to each activity. The RII was calculated for each risk to determine the most significant risk. The risks were classified according to the RII values assigned to each risk, and it proved feasible to find the most important risk element in megaprojects. As a result, we estimated the accurate rank using Excel to ensure that the activities received proper rankings. Based on these rankings, the impact on the project is determined, and appropriate measures are implemented to reduce or minimize the risk.

The table shows that the first rank has 2 activities, the third has 7 activities, the tenth has 3 activities, and the thirteenth has 2 activities, all of which share the same rank. It is because the likelihood and severity of the activities are equal. Hence, the RII value is the same for those actions. As a result, they share the same rank for several activities.

TOPSIS METHOD

In this TOPSIS approach, we calculate the rank using Pi values. Pi values are dependent on the probability and severity of each project activity. The approach includes a step-by-step procedure for calculating Pi values, as well as a small example for clarity. Pi values determine activity ranks and assign them accordingly. Table 8 shows the activities ordered in ascending rank order.

Table 8: Technical risks using TOPSIS

TOPSIS METHOD						
Activities	Probability	Severity	Risk impact/ level	Pi value	rank	accurate rank
Welding spatters	5	5	25	1	1	1
Lifting coils/Loading coil depender	4	5	20	0.64492	2	2
Use of Threading machine	4	5	20	0.64492	2	3
Strand cutting	4	5	20	0.64492	2	4
Stressing	4	5	20	0.64492	2	5
Flying particles, noise, dust, moving parts, untrained operators.	4	5	20	0.64492	2	6
No approved plan and design	4	5	20	0.64492	2	7
Receiving, offloading storage of posttensioning Equipment and materials	4	4	16	0.41968	8	8
Manual handling	4	4	16	0.41968	8	9
Grouting	4	4	16	0.41968	8	10
Emergency Rescue Response	4	4	16	0.41968	8	11
Electricity	3	5	15	0.35708	12	12
Fire and/or explosion when cylinder are stationed for use	3	5	15	0.35708	12	13
Welding and gas cutting works	3	4	12	0.24767	14	14
Mobilization/demobilization of plant and equipment to/from site	4	3	12	0.24767	14	15
Lifting/Offloading of material by lifting equipment	4	3	12	0.24767	14	16
Formwork Installation including shuttering & de-shuttering	4	3	12	0.24767	14	17
Night Shift Work	4	3	12	0.24767	14	18
Shifting and placing by crane/gantry	3	4	12	0.24767	14	19
Placing of shuttering on bed	3	4	12	0.24767	14	20

In these technological risks, Pi values are calculated for each activity. The Pi values fluctuate according on the probability and severity of the activity. The Pi values determine the Ranks assigned to each activity. Here Some activities have the same Pi value and hence share the same rank. As a result, we estimated the accurate rank using Excel to ensure that the activities received proper rankings. Based on these rankings, the impact on the project is determined, and appropriate measures are implemented to reduce or minimize the risk.

Table 9 : Rank Obtained Using TOPSIS method

TOPSIS METHOD						
Activities	Probability	Severity	Risk impact/level	Pi value	rank	accurate rank
slip, trip, and falls	5	5	25	1	1	1
eye irritation from radiation	5	5	25	1	1	2
Adverse weather condition	4	5	20	0.621036	3	3
Extreme high winds, heat, humidity	4	5	20	0.621036	3	4
head, eye, hearing, foot, hand injuries	4	5	20	0.621036	3	5
work platform	4	5	20	0.621036	3	6
radiated heat	4	5	20	0.621036	3	7
gas leaks	4	5	20	0.621036	3	8
flash back	4	5	20	0.621036	3	9
Chemical handling storage disposal	4	4	16	0.621036	3	10
Summer works	4	4	16	0.621036	3	11
unprotected voids	4	4	16	0.621036	3	12
extreme weather	3	5	15	0.336821	13	13
fragile surface	3	5	15	0.336821	13	14
General site activities	4	3	12	0.190076	15	15

The table 9 shows that the second rank has 6 activities, the eighth rank has 4 activities, the 12th level has 2 activities, and the 14th rank has 7 activities, all with the same rank. It is because the likelihood and severity of the activities are equal. As a result, the pi value remains consistent throughout operations. As a result, they share the same rank for several activities

Non-Technical Risks:

In this TOPSIS approach, we calculate the rank using Pi values. These Pi values are calculated depending on the likelihood and severity of the activity on the project. The approach includes a step-by-step procedure for calculating Pi values, as well as a brief sample. Based on these Pi values, ranks are determined for each activity and assigned to them. The activities are listed in ascending order of rank below Table 9.

Leading risks are ranked using the TOPSIS Method. The TOPSIS was calculated for each risk to determine which was the most serious. The risks were prioritised according to the Pi values assigned to each risk, and it was feasible to find the most relevant risk element in megaprojects. In these technological risks, Pi values are calculated for each activity. The Pi values fluctuate depending on the probability and severity of the activity. The Pi values determine the Ranks assigned to each activity. Here Some activities have the save Pi value, therefore they share the same rank. As a result, we estimated the accurate rank using Excel to ensure that the activities received proper rankings.

The project's impact is assessed based on these rankings, and efforts are taken to reduce or minimise the risk. The table shows that the first rank has two activities, the third rank has seven, the tenth rank has three, and the thirteenth rank has two, all with the same rank. It is because the likelihood and severity of the activities are equal. As a result, the Pi value remains consistent throughout operations. As a result, they share the same rank for several activities.

Comparing three methods: WSM/SAW, RII, and TOPSIS

The ranks for all activities are compared to ensure that they are accurate and precise. This comparison is done using the relative correlation coefficient (RCC) approach. Using this strategy, we can determine whether the rankings are correct or not. The correlation coefficient is calculated with the formula $\rho = 1 - ((6\sum d^2)/(n*(n^2-1)))$. The ρ value ranges between -1 and +1. If the ρ value is +1, the ranks are accurate; if the ρ value is -1, the ranks are the exact reverse. Table 10 shows a comparison of tanks for all three approaches for technical and non-technical risks.

Based on these ranks the impact on the project is known and accordingly, the measures are taken accordingly to minimise or mitigate the risk. As we can see in the above table, the 1st rank has 2 activities, 3rd rank has 7 activities, 10th rank has 3activities and 13th rank has 2 activities which share same ranks respectively. It is because the probability and severity of the activities are same. Hence the Pi value is also same for those activities. So, they share same rank for different activities.

Table 10. Technical risks comparison of methods

Technical risks Activities	WSM/SAW rank	RII rank	TOPSIS rank	ρ value	Accurate rank
Welding spatters	1	1	1	1	1
Lifting coils/Loading coil dipender	2	2	2	1	2
Use of Threading machine	2	2	2	1	3
Strand cutting	2	2	2	1	4
Stressing	2	2	2	1	5
Flying particles, noise, dust, moving parts, untrained operators.	2	2	2	1	6
No approved plan and design	2	2	2	1	7
Receiving, offloading storage of posttensioning Equipment and materials	8	8	8	1	8
Manual handling	8	8	8	1	9
Grouting	8	8	8	1	10
Emergency Rescue Response	8	8	8	1	11
Electricity	12	12	12	1	12
Fire and/or explosion when cylinder are stationed for use	12	12	12	1	13
welding and gas cutting works	14	14	14	1	14

Mobilisation/demobilisation of plant and equipment to/from site	14	14	14	1	15
Lifting/Offloading of material by lifting equipment	14	14	14	1	16
Formwork Installation including shuttering & de- shuttering	14	14	14	1	17
Night Shift Work	14	14	14	1	18
Shifting and placing by crane/gantry	14	14	14	1	19
Placing of shuttering on bed	14	14	14	1	20

The ρ value of 1 in the table above indicates that all ranks of activities using the three approaches are accurate and exact. The activities listed below have a rank of 1,2,8,12,14, indicating that they each take an equal proportion of risk in the project. If risk minimization is to be accomplished in the project, risk should be reduced in these activities so that it affects the entire project and reduces the total risk in Table 11.

Table 11. Non-Technical Risks comparison of methods

NON-Technical risks Activities	WSM/SAW rank	RII rank	TOPSIS rank	ρ value	accurate rank
slip, trip, and falls	1	1	1	1	1
eye irritation from radiation	1	1	1	1	2
Adverse weather condition	2	2	2	1	3
Extreme high winds, heat, humidity	2	2	2	1	4
head, eye, hearing, foot, hand injuries	2	2	2	1	5
work platform	2	2	2	1	6
radiated heat	2	2	2	1	7
gas leaks	2	2	2	1	8
flash back	2	2	2	1	9
Chemical handling storage disposal	2	2	2	1	10
Summer works	2	2	2	1	11
unprotected voids	2	2	2	1	12
extreme weather	13	13	13	1	13
fragile surface	13	13	13	1	14
General site activities	15	15	15	1	15

The ρ value in the two table10 and table 11 is 1, indicating accurate and precise rankings. The rankings for all three approaches are correct and exact. The activities indicated below have a rank of 1, indicating that they take an equal level of risk in the project. If risk minimisation in the project is to be achieved, risk minimisation in these activities must occur so that it affects the entire project and reduces total risk.

Conclusion:

Risks in any project can be avoided or reduced when they are clearly identified. In the current study, various risk factors in megaprojects are a big problem that cause significant damage. The current study investigated both technical and non-technical site risks in megaprojects using several methodologies. The most important item highlighted is that machinery should be handled properly. Everyone on site is responsible for taking all necessary safety precautions. Every worker should be taught safety on a daily basis. Management and monitoring should be done properly. All drivers and operators of heavy machinery must be inducted before entering the site and operating moving plant and machinery. Site speed limitations must always be followed along the routes.

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